

Quantum-Safe Migration Playbook (v1.2.0)

A strategic knowledge base for the move to post-quantum cryptography (PQC). Written for CISOs, system architects, and security engineers who need to turn a theoretical cryptographic risk into a dated operational plan.

What's in this bundle

File	Who uses it	What it's for
<code>README.md</code>	Anyone	This overview. Start here.
<code>Quantum_Safe_Strategy_Corpus.md</code>	Strategists, AI engineers	The source of truth. Structured facts with IDs, cross-references, and scope boundaries.
<code>INTEGRATION.md</code>	AI engineers	How to ingest the corpus into a RAG system, plus the system prompt.
<code>evals/golden_queries.md</code>	AI engineers	Retrieval tests with pass/fail criteria and distractors.
<code>CHANGELOG.md</code>	Maintainers	Version history.

The original deck (`Quantum-Safe Migration Playbook.pptx`) is the visual narrative. This bundle is the text version you feed into systems, policies, and RFPs.

The four risks the corpus covers

The playbook's operational claim is that four risk categories, taken together, define whether a migration succeeds or slips:

- Hardware.** Legacy ASICs, bootloader trust stores, HSMS, VPN appliances. Covered in §5.
- Latency and bandwidth.** Larger keys and signatures change handshake behavior on real networks. Covered in §4.
- Vendor readiness.** Distinguishing shipped-and-verified from PowerPoint-promise. Covered in §9.
- Discovery.** Finding every place crypto already lives. Covered in §6.

If your migration plan does not have an owner for each of these, it has a gap.

How to use this (pick one)

If you are writing strategy or policy: open the corpus and use the section structure as a scaffold. Copy fact IDs into your internal docs so reviewers can trace claims back.

If you are running the playbook as an AI advisor: follow `INTEGRATION.md` to set up retrieval. Run the golden queries in `evals/` before you let anyone use the system.

If you are evaluating vendors: read §9 of the corpus. The RFP clauses and the red-flags list are ready to paste into procurement documents.

If you are building a program plan: read §1.3 (federal timelines), §3 (what to protect first), §8 (how to pilot). That's enough to size the effort.

What this bundle does not give you

- Physics of quantum computing. Out of scope.
- Quantum Key Distribution (QKD). Different technology, different threat model.
- Specific product or vendor recommendations.
- Legal compliance interpretation.
- A Q-Day prediction.

The corpus says "no" to these explicitly so your RAG system doesn't invent answers.

Version and freshness

Current: **v1.2.0**, last reviewed **April 2026**.

Two facts move fast and should be re-checked every quarter: the Q-Day timeline (§1.4) and the deployment percentage (§2.1). See [CHANGELOG.md](#) for what changed between versions.